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Online Teaching and Learning: Innovation for Promoting Equality of Educational Opportunity in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Covid-19 is one global health challenge whose outbreak brought about much creative insights and awareness which when carefully, critically and creatively explored can ignite revolutions for the systematic development of man and his institutions. The education industry is one institution where developments occasioned by the outbreak of covid-19 have potentials for repositioning education for higher accessibility, greater productivity and visibility. The outbreak created creative, critical and robust insights on education particularly increasing access to it. Using the philosophical methodology and guided by social constructivism, this study discusses online teaching and learning as an innovation that was occasioned by the outbreak of covid-19 and highlights its potentials in promoting equality of educational opportunity in Nigeria among other values that promise reforming, transforming and revolutionizing education. The paper makes recommendations, part of which is that reforms and transformations brought about by the outbreak of covid-19 should be sustained and stakeholders in education, principally the government should ensure that all the necessary conditions that support online teaching and learning are available in educational institutions among others.

Keywords: Online teaching and learning, equality of educational opportunity, covid-19, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION:

The outbreak of corona-virus otherwise called covid-19 is one global event that cannot be forgotten in a hurry. The outbreak of the virus caused epical and phenomenal social, economic, political and general disruptions and disarticulations across the globe. It was first a health challenge that metamorphosed into a social, economic, political, moral, scientific and technological issues that brought the world to a standstill within a couple of days. The outbreak of the virus exposed many things and at the same time laid foundations for many new development and new beginnings. This is the reason why many scholars and institutions describe the outbreak of the various as a challenge and an opportunity (Nwaokugha, 2020).

It can be said that no country in the world, whether developed, developing or underdeveloped had state of the art infrastructure that can enable them put up effective fight as at the time of the outbreak of the virus. What this points hand to is that states, irrespective of their developmental sophistication or lack of it had infrastructural and personnel deficits that did not enable them put up effective and meaningful fight or effective response to the rampaging onslaught of the virus but such states remained vulnerable, helpless, frustrated and hopeless. It is also correct that the outbreak is associated with generating and stimulating

emotional instabilities-feelings of fear and instability across the length, and breadth of the world. In the face of mankind's frustration, helplessness, hopelessness, emotional and psychological instabilities, covid-19 keeps depreciating the quality of life of the people including making pessimism a norm in the day to day life of the people so much that no one reasons along lines of putting up investments or making investment decisions.

The outbreak of covid-19 can also not be forgotten in a hurry due to its ability to manifest conditions which scholars describe as mix bag, that is, the manifestation of conditions which on one hand is a challenge and on the other is an opportunity (Nwaokugha, 2020). One sector that is a victim as well as a beneficiary of the rampaging onslaught of covid-19 is the education industry. This has been observed in different forms by personalities and scholars across the world. In the words of Stefania Giannini, Assistant Director General, United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organizations (UNESCO), Robert Jenkins, Global Director, Education, United Nations International Children's Emergency Fund (UNICEF) and Jamie Saavedra, Director General, Education Global Practice, the World Bank "The global disruption to education caused by covid-19 pandemic constitutes the worst education crisis on record" This position is so taken because the outbreak of the virus brought about unplanned disruption and unplanned closure of educational institutions from the pre-primary to the tertiary levels and during this period of disruption and closure, staggering figures that scholars and institutions claim to be in the range of 1.5 billion (Vegas & Winthrop, 2020:4) and 1.6 billion (UNESCO, UNICEF and the World Bank, 2020:4) did not go to school. That such staggering number of learners was out of educational institutions can be confirmed in the assertion put up by Huber and Helm (2020:223) who write that the crisis caused by the covid-19 virus had far-reaching effects on education.

What seems to compound matters for education and learners across the globe during this period is that visible conditions that are associated with covid-19 such as fear, worry, anxiety, frustration, irritation, hopelessness, helplessness, insecurity, poverty and other social disarticulations are not good bed fellows or co-travelers with education (Nwaokugha & Frank-Keri, 2023:80). There is on the other hand an open acknowledgement that the outbreak of covid-19 is phenomenally and robustly associated with positive developments in the field of education. Many scholars are in agreement that the outbreak of covid-19 has rays of hope for education in particular and humanity in general. According to Vegas and Winthrop (2020:1), the outbreak of covid-19 has resulted in at least one positive thing: a much greater appreciation for the importance of public schools, a position they expressed in details in these words:

It is hard to imagine there will be another moment in history when the central role of education in the economic, social and political prosperity and stability of nations is so obvious and well understood by the general population. Now is the time to chart a vision for how education can emerge stronger from the global crisis than ever before and propose a path for capitalizing on education's newfound support in virtually every community across the globe (P.I)

It has also been asserted very authoritatively by UNESCO (2020) that the outbreak of covid-19 is associated with causing and triggering the biggest changes in education since public education emerged in the 19th Century. True, the outbreak of covid-19 has opened a floodgate of changes and innovations in education but one change that people are critically and creatively disposed to since the outbreak of covid-19 due to its transformative, revolutionary, human rights promotion potentials, creation of access and equality of education driven potentials is online teaching and learning. As an innovation, online teaching and learning is loaded with many benefits, but for the purposes of this study, focus shall be on the potentials of online teaching and learning in supporting and promoting equality of educational opportunity in Nigeria.

This study is unique and its uniqueness lies in its significance especially its ability to create inclusive opportunities through which citizens irrespective of barriers in distance and location can have unhindered access to flexible and robust education that is of equal quality with education provided and obtained through the conventional face to face teacher-student interactions in the classroom. What is implied here is that this study has potentials to create awareness that can enhance citizens' enjoyment of their rights to

education which fundamentally is every citizen's fundamental human rights without which the citizen is impaired and cannot maximally explore and have access to opportunities in the larger society. In fact, the awareness or increase to educational opportunities created through this study can add to the human capital development of Nigeria and humanity generally as more persons can acquire epistemological empowerment and on the basis of its associated strength and power participate more actively in the enterprise of national development through their effective participation in democracy, social, moral, economic, entrepreneurial and labour activities.

The multi-dimensional sphere of influence of covid-19, a development that gave rise to the embrace of online teaching and learning in education makes the philosophical research methodology with its interdisciplinary, multidisciplinary and cross disciplinary approaches most suitable and appropriate for the study. In fact, the suitability of this methodology is hinged on the fact that every human endeavor and every human experience benefits from the critical insights which this research methodology provides. This position has been acknowledged by Nwoke and Nwaokugha (2024:59), when they write that "every branch of knowledge benefits from philosophical reflections and this particular study is no exception". Philosophical research methodology is contemporarily the destination of choice of scholars and researchers and part of why this is so is that the methodology incorporates speculation, analysis and prescription that enables scholars and researchers indulge in what Nwaokugha and Gbendo (2026:11) call "the breaking of groundbreaking breakthroughs that can challenge scholars and researcher's into focusing their study on terrains and environments that may ordinarily remain unimaginable, un-contemplatable and unthinkable". Philosophical research methodology is noted for certain features; it uses extensive narrative data (Angadi, 2019) and the extensive narrative data is usually subjected to thorough analytic scrutiny and rigours of thought that target establishing semantic clarity and logical coherence (Nwaokugha & Moses, 2025), for this reason the instrument for data collection is usually the researcher(s) (Nwaokugha & Nworgu, 2026).

The theoretical framework upon which this study is based is social constructivism and according to Nwaokugha and Odinka (2025:18) invokes a meaning that simply means that human beings are the architects, builders and constructors of whatever meaning that exists in the world of knowledge. What had been said above about social constructivism is put slightly different by Nwaokugha (2025:24) that:

What is at the heart or centre of social constructivism as a theory of knowledge construction is the awareness that no knowledge of any configuration is ready made and correspondingly sampled or displayed anywhere to be purchased or hired by who wants its, rather knowledge of any configuration can be produced, generated and constructed through the conscious, critical and creative efforts of an individual or individuals who demonstrate creative engagement, commitment and critical consciousness in the search for knowledge.

A revelation which the above points hands to, is that personal experience of whoever wants to build and construct knowledge and the environment he is, plays critical and key roles in influencing the person's endeavor at knowledge building and construction.

A known practice with academic studies that employ the philosophical research methodology is to give in depth and detailed attention to key concepts that constitute the study and to this we now turn.

Online teaching and Learning

Any society or state that toils with education pays dearly for it as education is a worthy investment and a worthy legacy that any responsible parent and any responsible state can bequeath to its present and future generations. There are many justifications why a responsible parent and a responsible state can prioritize the provision of education for its sons, daughters and wards or why a responsible state can prioritize the provision of education for her citizens. The commitment of parents towards education for their sons, daughters and wards derives justifications from the fact that parents want their sons, daughters and wards to be better than them in all ramifications and quality education is the route for translating this vision into reality. The state equally shows epical interests in education for the citizens because more than any other

institution, the state relies more on education for the reformation and transformation of the citizens including bringing about innovations that can in addition to improving the quality of life of the citizens, reposition the state for greater visibility. It is correct to say that parents and the state are co-travelers on the same road in matters of education for members of the state and that both parents and the state have strong conviction that education is a strong instrument and institution for repositioning, reorienting, sensitizing and conscientizing the citizens in readiness for arming citizens with critical and creative capital for survival and for responding to challenges that occur in split seconds in the day to day affairs of man in the society or state. The global community is also very much aware of the values of education and pragmatically demonstrate this during the global rampaging spree of covid-19 by quickly directing the global community to switch over to online teaching and learning.

Online lone teaching and learning as an innovation in education has been in existence in developed countries of the world especially where there are suitable information and communication technology (ICT) infrastructure and adequate skilled manpower to maintain it (Nwaokugha & Wogonwu, 2023:7), but it is a sudden and novel educational innovation in most of the developing and underdeveloped countries of the world, that out of circumstances simply embraced the innovation as a response and adjustment mechanism for continuous provision of education to their citizens in the face of the ravaging and rampaging spree of covid-19. Response to outline teaching and learning has been very receptive since its emergency and sudden embrace by educational institutions and there is one thing that this communicates: The degree of receptivity with which educational institutions especially in developing and underdeveloped states have embraced online teaching and learning is a testimony that it has come to stay and has become a trending destination of choice that any teacher or learner who wants to remain relevant in the knowledge industry of the 21st century and beyond cannot do without. A proof of the popularity and receptivity of online teaching and learning across the world can be established in the way it has become a trending focal flashpoint and centre of attraction among scholars so much so that there are galaxy of definitions of the concept. Attention is drawn to this by Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:7), who write that online teaching and learning,

Attracts a lot of scholarly attention so much that it goes by different names such as e-learning and virtual learning and to be expected, it does not have a one size fit all definition rather it has many definitions that reflect areas of interests of scholars who show interests in online teaching and learning so much that one scholar may provide more than one definition.

In line with the above, Basar, Mansor, Jamaludin and Alias (2021:12) define online teaching and learning (e-learning) as any form of pedagogy delivered using digital technology. In the same line of thinking, Oblinger, Oblinger and Lyppincott (2005) write that online teaching and learning illuminates meaning which describes teaching and learning situation where learners learn outside the formal classroom setting usually by using online platforms. What may be considered as an inclusive definition of online teaching and learning is provided by Nwaokugha and Keri-Frank (2023:86) in these words:

What any insightful observer can observe in all efforts at defining online teaching and learning is that all such attempts invoke meanings that revolve around teaching and learning through the use of devices that are technology driven and connected to the internet and this connection to the internet makes teaching and learning available to learners anywhere, anytime irrespective of distance, location or environment. Put slightly different, online teaching and learning revolves around the use of electronic and telecommunication gadget and digital facilities, hardware and software and technology in teaching and learning processes where the tradition face to face social interaction or in person instruction between the teacher and the learner in a structured classroom setting or environment may not apply, rather

teaching and learning take place irrespective of distance and location of the teacher and his or her learners.

Having provided detailed explanations of online teaching and learning, it is important to point out that success in deploying it in instruction in educational institutions is heavily dependent on the availability of steady source of power or electricity, digital technology, availability of a population that has mastery of knowledge of technology and the use of technological accessories. Without the availability of all the above, in a manner that has no space for compromise, online teaching and learning will remain a distant dream.

There are basically two modes through which online teaching and learning can be made available to members of the society or can be translated into reality and the two modes are synchronous and asynchronous modes. Synchronous mode of online teaching and learning is where opportunity is provided in the course of online teaching and learning for responses, feedbacks, actions and activities at real time or at the same time of online teaching and learning between the teacher and the students. Features that are unique here are the presence of the teacher and the learners and spontaneous feedback in the forms of immediate or on the spot communication between the teacher and his learners at the moment of teaching and learning. Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:9) write that “good example of synchronous approach to online teaching and learning include live charts, audio and videoconferencing, data and application sharing, virtual hand raising, shared whiteboard and joint viewing of multimedia presentation and online slide shows. There is always a prescheduled time for the online class to hold.

On the other hand asynchronous mode of online teaching and learning is the opposite of synchronous mode and what this means is that the online teaching and learning is not undertaken in time but is documented and presented in the form of a tape recorded documentation, which the learner can play or access at his convenient time, anywhere the learner deems it free, fit and convenient to do so. What is revealed here is that the teacher makes his instruction available to learners without any form of interaction with them. According to Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:9), examples of asynchronous modes to online teaching and learning include the use of e-mail, newsgroup and bulletin boards, file attachments and other systems that can save whatever instructions the teacher has for the learners. An advantage that can be credited to the asynchronous mode according to Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:9) is that learners can learn whatever the teacher has for them at any time they deem it fit and convenient while a disadvantage that is associated with it is that it has no provision for feedback from teachers or fellow learners.

From whichever angle online teaching and learning is considered, one fundamental variable is sure: online teaching and learning has multifaceted advantages and of all these advantages, one advantage stands out. Online teaching and learning is a vibrant foundation for actualizing and translating equality of educational opportunity into reality.

Equality of Educational Opportunity

It is ideal and appropriate that any discussion that is focused on equality of educational opportunity should start with a critical and creative look at the concept of equality, which as a concept is at the centre discussions that focus on issues of distribution of social goods among members of the society. On the basis of this, equality is a socio-moral, socio-political and a concept upon which economic considerations and decisions are made. The many areas of focus of the concept of equality one concept that is attractive to many scholars and many disciplines and correspondingly one concept that does not easily yield itself to a one size fits all definition.

One plausible reason for the attractiveness of equality to disciplines and scholars is the conviction among scholars that equality is the pillar of order, stability and social harmony as it produces fundamental conditions under which citizens in a state can have access to social goods as well as ensures that fairness prevails in the distribution of whatever social goods the state makes available to the citizens. In fact, making equality a norm in a state gives everyone a sense of belonging to cooperatively work for the progress and development of the state but undermining equality triggers civil disobedience, anarchy,

protest and formation of social movements that prioritize clamour for revolutions and social change especially social changes that are deep rooted in justice, fairness and equity.

To be expected of equality as a concept that is attractive to many disciplines and scholars is the inability of equality to yield to a one size fits all definition. The absence of a univocal definition for equality makes it a polymorphous concept in the hand of scholars. Interestingly laymen associate equality with the idea of sameness or identicalness in the treatment of people but unfortunately in practice or reality, there are context in which sameness or identicalness may apply and may not apply in discussions of equality. This is the enigma of equality and resolving it follows trajectories where conscious provisions are made for pluralism in human affairs and not view the concept from the lens of identicalness or sameness in the treatment of people and again discussions that are centred on equality are usually context specific.

Context-specificity is necessary in discussions that are focused on equality and education is a focal flashpoint in such discussion across the globe. Like equality, the concept of equality or equality of educational opportunity does not admit a one size fits all definition rather in practice, it opens itself up to many meanings and interpretations. In all of these, one thing of interest is that all such definitions, meanings and interpretations derive from the central idea of equality of educational opportunity, which Aksu and Canturk (2015:79) write “implies that educational services should be accessible to everyone respectful of their abilities and interest”. Such educational services upon which the meaning of equality of educational opportunity revolves leave the concept of equality of educational opportunity in practice with multiple provisions, any of which or in combination are part of the meaning of the concept. Therefore, any state that makes provision whereby there is: i.Equal right of every citizen to access education in the state (i.e. build school for the citizens). ii.Recognizes and upholds the right of every citizen to equal education (provides same curriculum, syllabus, textbooks for all learners). iii. Establishes criteria for equal achievement (in the case of letter grades for school subjects) can be said to have made equality of educational opportunity available and a norm in the state. What had been said above about equality of educational opportunity can be said to reflect and incorporate (i) access (ii) participation, and (iii) results. Having discussed equality of educational opportunity as shown above, focus can shift on how online teaching and learning as an innovation promotes equality of educational opportunity.

How online teaching and learning can promote equality of educational opportunity

Education is universally recognized as a social good that individuals, institutions and the state strive to provide for the citizens and the extent in which states make education a priority among social services that they provide determine the quality of human capital, a vector that is critical for the development of the state. It is also correct that the level of development in the education system of a state is a fundamental index for determining the level of respect and honour that a state receives in comity of states. As a result of the above, states make it part of their statutory responsibility to heavily invest in education or alternatively initiate policies, programmes and practical actions for purposes of ensuring that every citizen of the state has quality access to education or more technically there is equality of educational opportunity for every citizen. Policies, programmes and practical actions have seen states take collaborative, joint venture and innovative actions that allow the private sector to participate actively in education and its provision but success in achieving equality of educational opportunity has remained minimal or entirely elusive. However, there is in recent times a ray of hope and flashes of optimism for making equality of educational reality and this ray of hope and flashes of optimism are coming from the direction of online teaching and learning.

Online teaching and learning is one hundred percent dependent on digital technologies and other accessories, ranging from internet, computers, hard and software devices and these devices share certain features in common namely removing barriers in distance and getting to every region of the world irrespective of the difficulties in the terrain. Development in information and computer technology and their integration into education have been great assets in education as education has leveraged on it to expand in all ramifications in the area of improved instruction and becoming more accessible to citizens. In fact, the deployment of computers and internet facilities in education or more precisely the integration of information and computer technology into teaching and learning (online teaching and learning) has

potentials to increase educational opportunities in the form of citizens who due to one level of difficulty or the other could not have access to formal education, but are interested and desirous to acquire formal education, such person can now have access to formal education at their door step through online teaching and learning. How this can be translated into reality is buttressed by Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:10) when they write that:

Online teaching and learning grants and permits learners access to learning irrespective of distance, time and space, meaning that with the online teaching and learning platforms, teachers and learners are free to link up to any online platforms of their choice at their preferred time.

It is true that many persons across the world live in difficult environments where transportation in and out of such environment is a herculean and uphill task, a development that denies them opportunities of going to school. In this case, the availability of online teaching and learning removes this barrier, a development that has potential to open up floodgate of educational opportunities for anyone who is desirous of going to school. This is what Aksu and Canturk (2015:80) call attention to when they write that “the integration of information technology into the curriculum promotes internet access and networked educational opportunities for students in small schools in rural areas”.

Making available access to education or equality of educational opportunity aside, online teaching and learning exposes learners to the best quality instructions that can be available on any topic across the globe as well as opportunity to learn under the guidance of the best teachers in the world. A revelation this points hand to is that in addition to making available quality instructions for the epistemological empowerment of the learner, online teaching and learning helps to ignite innovations in the education industry that improves the professional development of the teacher, helps to introduce sustainable innovations in education as well as helps to add quality to the growth of the teaching profession. The implications of these for equality of educational opportunity is that every learners’ interests so far education is concerned can be provided for as learners have alternatives to choose from.

Online teaching and learning as a sustainable platform for promoting equality of educational opportunity makes the acquisition of learning and education more flexible for the teacher and the learner. Its flexibility also makes it possible for learners to identify with any programme of their choice at their own pace and convenience. In fact, the excuse that one is working and correspondingly may not proceed with his or her education can be said to be a thing of the past in a regime where online teaching and learning is the norm. What boosts and promotes equality of educational opportunity especially through online teaching and learning is highlighted by Nwaokugha and Wogonwu (2023:11) in these words:

Online teaching and learning can be said to be cost effective as learners cannot pay for transportation to get to their institutions and their learning cannot be impaired or compromised by the inability of learners’ institutions or state to provide building infrastructure. This means that with the necessary technologies and digital devices, online teaching and learning has all what it takes to go on irrespective of deficits in building infrastructure and personnel.

What is implied here is that online teaching and learning in its mission of equalizing educational opportunities for every citizen promotes teaching and learning in a manner that the teacher teaches the learner at his convenience and the learner equally learns at his convenience. As an instructional process that supports and promotes flexibility, online teaching and learning avoids teachers and learners’ opportunity to connect with one another any day any time and ask questions or interact concerning what had been taught and learnt. This measure of freedom which online teaching and learning is associated with provides so much dividends in promoting equality of educational opportunity.

The power of online teaching and learning to promote equality of educational opportunity can be acknowledged in its receptivity and capacity to make provisions for the floating of more courses and programmes. That online teaching and learning is synonymous with revolutions in programme expansion points in the direction that it has the capacity to raise literacy levels to heights where citizens can fulfill their educational dreams and aspirations.

Online teaching and learning is a recipe for increasing educational opportunity as it saves cost for learners as well as cost for investors in education. The implication here is that investors in education can easily do so and their participation in education can help citizens in providing solutions and resolving issues of access to education.

CONCLUSION

There is no vacuum and stagnation in nature and the society replicates this on a daily basis by making innovations a regular occurrence in the efforts of man. Education as an institution has been at the centre of generating ideas for the society's day to day innovations in the affairs of man, where on the other hand, education also functions as an institution for fashioning out strategies for effective and efficient distribution of the social goods of the society. Marrying together the philosophy of functioning as a spring board for engineering innovations and offering society strategies for effective and efficient patterns through which the social goods of the society can be distributed, education particularly in developing and underdeveloped countries of the world recently popularized online teaching and learning as an innovation through which the society can promote and achieve equality of educational opportunity. These developments are in line with education living up to expectations as the innovation hub of the society and the direction the society should look upto in terms of generating ideas for addressing the problems of humanity.

The efforts of stakeholders in education to by way of innovation resort to online teaching and learning as a way of equalizing educational opportunity has produced and will continue to produce excellent results for the members of the society. There is now among the citizens a conscious awareness that one can study and receive instructions from the comfort of his home, study while he works and at a speed that is flexible and convenient for the learner, have access to the best materials in his chosen area of study and under the tutorship of the best teachers in the world, opens floodgate of opportunities for the learner to become a global citizen and acquire global experiences through his constant interactions with the internet. All the above are in addition to the fact that online teaching and learning is cost effective particularly in the provision of building infrastructure. This particular feature of online teaching and learning strongly points in the direction that it is investor and learner friendly and the implication is phenomenal certainty in increase in equality of educational opportunity.

Having itemized how online teaching and learning can promote equality of educational opportunity, it is equally important we say that online teaching and learning is not a bed of roses, meaning that anyone who is desirous of leveraging on its potentials for the promotion of equality of educational opportunity can ensure certain conditions are met and on the basis of this observation, we make the following recommendations. There should be steady supply of power on the part of investors and on the part of network providers, there should be improved supply of network. Teachers and instructors to be employed should have the professional expertise and learners should comfort themselves by behaving well whenever they are participating in online teaching and learning session. Lastly, society should accord equal recognition to those who obtain their degrees and certificates from online programmes the same status that is given to those who obtain theirs from the regular conventional programmes.

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